

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN CEO PAY AND FIRM PERFORMANCE: AN ANALYSIS OF PRIVATE AND PUBLIC INDIAN LISTED FIRMS

Mr Sameer Kathuria

Research Scholar, Aligarh Muslim University

CMA CS Dr S.K.Gupta

Managing Director , ICMAI RVO, Lodhi Road, New Delhi - 110003

Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to examine the relationship between executive compensation and firm performance of Private and Public Indian listed firms. The data of 199 listed Indian firms on NSE was downloaded from prowest database for the period 2011 to 2017. The data were analyzed using panel least square method. The findings reveal that there is weak positive relationship between executive compensation and firm performance when accounting based measure are applied and statistically non-significant relationship when market based measures are used. Further Executive compensation is more significantly correlated with size in case of Private Firms than in case of Public firms. This analysis provides an insight for the stakeholders to analyze the reasons behind exorbitant executive compensation.

Keywords executive compensation, firm performance, panel least square

INTRODUCTION

Over the past decade, there has been a significant increase in executive compensation that has outpaced the growth of the companies they lead. This excessive CEO pay can negatively impact shareholders' wealth, especially when it is not aligned with the organization's performance. It is essential for stakeholders to remain vigilant in monitoring and addressing extravagant compensation packages for chief executive officers. This issue has been a central focus in the corporate governance debate, with extensive research conducted in developed economies such as the US and UK, as well as in some developing economies like China. However, the relationship between executive compensation and firm performance in India has received limited attention.

In this study, our objective is to investigate the connection between executive pay and firm performance in India. We measure executive pay by considering the total remuneration received by the chief executive officer or managing director of the company. Our analysis incorporates both accounting and market-based performance measures, along with firm-specific variables such as size, leverage, and risk, as these factors can influence the relationship between pay and performance. The research focuses on the following sub-objectives:

- To examine the relationship between executive compensation and return on assets.
- To investigate the relationship between executive compensation and return on net worth.
- To explore the relationship between executive compensation and overall return.

- To compare the pay-performance relationship between private and public companies listed on the National Stock Exchange (NSE).

For data analysis, we utilize EViews software, which offers powerful and user-friendly tools for econometric analysis, forecasting, and simulation. Our study utilizes a list of companies from the NIFTY 500, the largest stock exchange in India, representing over 95% of the stocks listed on the NSE. The study period covers the years 2011 to 2017.

This study contributes to the existing literature in three significant ways. Firstly, it addresses a research gap by focusing on a more recent period from 2011 to 2017, considering the potential impacts of the unprecedented COVID-19 pandemic on the data. Secondly, while previous research on this topic has predominantly focused on developed economies like the US and UK, and to a lesser extent on developing economies like China, the Indian context offers substantial opportunities for exploration. Lastly, this study provides stakeholders with valuable insights into the growing relationship between CEO compensation and firm performance, enabling them to analyze the necessity and significance of high executive compensation.

The paper is organized into five sections. Section 2 provides an overview of the existing literature on executive compensation and firm performance. Section 3 outlines the methodology employed in this study. In Section 4, we present the details of the estimation and analysis procedures. Finally, the paper concludes with Section 5, which presents the study's findings, recommendations, and limitations.

Literature review

The topic of executive compensation and firm performance has received extensive attention from scholars and researchers. Conducting a literature review enables the incorporation of existing knowledge, which can be further enhanced through the contributions of this study. Among the over 400 research papers on executive compensation found in the Scopus database spanning the past 40 years (Frydman & Jenter, 2010), the relationship between executive compensation and firm performance has been a subject of significant interest.

Executive Compensation Components:

“One frequently observed compensation package, as described by Frydman and Jenter (2010), includes five basic components: annual salary, annual bonus, long-term incentive plan payouts, stock option grants, and restricted stock grants.

Measurement of Firm Performance:

Various tools can be employed to measure firm performance, depending on industry characteristics, study objectives, and the subject under investigation. Financial performance, which assesses an organization's success and growth potential, is commonly utilized (Ahmadi et al., 2018; Focke et al., 2017; Kim & Han, 2018; Kanapathippillai et al., 2019; Al Farooque et al., 2019; Sridhar & Kumar, 2015; Raithatha & Komera, 2016; S. S. K. Jaiswall & Bhattacharyya, 2016).

Previous Studies and Findings:

Researchers have explored the antecedents and consequences of the relationship between executive compensation and firm performance. Jensen and Meckling (1976) found a positive and statistically significant relationship between CEO compensation and shareholders' wealth. Hall

and Liebman (1998) provided empirical evidence supporting a strong positive relation between executive compensation and firm performance based on a 15-year panel data analysis of publicly traded U.S. companies. Murphy (1999) demonstrated that executive compensation practices vary based on company size, industry, and country, highlighting that stock-based compensation is not the sole driving force behind executive compensation.

Research in Emerging Markets:

While extensive research on executive compensation and firm performance has been conducted in developed countries, such as the United States, United Kingdom, Canada, and Germany, it is crucial to study emerging markets due to differences in firm structure and market characteristics. Studies by Gallego and Larrain (2012) in Argentina, Brazil, and Chile, and Kato and Long (2006) in China, have shed light on the relationship between executive compensation and firm performance in these markets.

Indian Context:

Several studies focused on Indian firms have explored the determinants and consequences of executive compensation. Sridhar and Kumar (2015) examined the influence of various variables on determining executive compensation, while Raithatha and Komera (2016) investigated the pay-performance relationship among Indian firms. Ramaswamy et al. (2018) categorized the determinants of executive compensation into human capital and governance variables. Ghosh (2006) identified four determinants of CEO compensation in the Indian context: firm performance, internal monitoring, personal attributes of the CEO, and other firm factors.

Contributions and Gap in the Literature:

Despite extensive research, empirical findings on the relationship between executive compensation and firm performance have been inconclusive. Therefore, further research is warranted. This study aims to bridge the gap by considering a more recent period from 2011 to 2017, exploring the Indian context, and providing stakeholders with insights into the increasing relationship between CEO compensation and firm performance.

This comprehensive review of previous research highlights the significance of the relationship between executive compensation and firm performance. By incorporating existing knowledge and addressing research gaps, this study aims to contribute to the understanding of executive compensation practices and their impact on firm performance.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The data for this paper has been obtained from the prowess database maintained by the Centre for Monitoring Economy (CMIE). The prowess database contains financial statements of over 20,000 Indian firms and provides information on various financial and non-financial variables such as assets, sales, EPS, PE ratios, salary, designation, and more. Previous studies on various topics, including executive compensation and firm performance, have utilized this database.

The sample selection process involved considering the NIFTY 500 companies to examine the relationship between executive compensation and firm performance. NIFTY is the largest stock exchange in India and represents more than 95% of the stocks listed on the NSE. The study period covers the years 2011 to 2017. Financial service firms were excluded from the sample due to

regulatory considerations. Additionally, firms with insufficient or incomplete data were also excluded. The final sample consists of 199 firms with 1,271 observations over a span of 7 years. Among the 199 firms, 173 firms with 1,081 observations are classified as private, while 26 firms with 135 observations are categorized as public.

Regarding the selection of variables, the study aims to examine the relationship between executive pay and performance. The total remuneration received by the chief executive officer or managing director of the company is considered as the measure of executive pay. Performance is measured using both accounting-based and market-based measures, as previous studies have employed these measures to analyze the pay-performance relationship. Additionally, firm-specific variables such as size, leverage, and risk are included as they can potentially influence the pay-performance relationship.

The data analysis for this study is performed using EViews software. EViews is a powerful and user-friendly statistical, forecasting, and modeling tool commonly used for econometric analysis, forecasting, and simulation.

Research Objective

The main objective of this paper is to examine the relationship between executive compensation and firm performance. This objective has been divided into three sub objectives

- To examine the relationship between executive compensation and return on assets.
- To investigate the relationship between executive compensation and return on net worth.
- To explore the relationship between executive compensation and overall return.
- To compare the pay-performance relationship between private and public companies listed on the National Stock Exchange (NSE).

ESTIMATION PROCEDURE AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive analysis

Descriptive statistics summarizes the basic characteristics of data in a meaningful ways. Measure of central tendency and measure of variability are the two basic categories of Descriptive statistics. Mean and Median have been used to represent the data and standard deviation have been used to measure the variability in the data. Table I summarizes the sample firm characteristics in terms of executive compensation, return on net worth, and return on total assets, returns, leverage and Tobin Q.

Table I

Description of variables considered in the study.

Variables	Description
ROA	Ratio of earnings before interest and taxes to total assets
ROE	Ratio of profit after tax to book value of equity
Q	Ratio of market value of equity and book value of equity
RET	Annual stock return
SIZE	Natural logarithm of total assets
LEV	Ratio of total borrowings to total assets
RISK	It refers to company beta calculated considering BSE Sensex as the market index

Table II Descriptive statistics of the sample

Variables	No. of observation	Mean	Median	Maximum	Minimum	Standard deviation	Skewness	kurtosis
Log exec return	1384	7.391021	7.446753	9.218982	3.698970	0.577094	-0.648027	5.315599
ROA	1436	8.113948	6.785000	32.88000	-73.7500	7.801674	-0.638740	14.34979
ROE	1432	15.89366	16.09000	427.7800	-1109.110	41.40354	-17.40516	459.2624
LEVERAGE	1414	0.118324	0.072979	.935785	0	.135867	1.394090	5.199491
TOBIN Q	1449	4.996099	3.048499	266.8519	-47.99703	11.30930	15.11729	315.2142
SIZE	1414	4.727217	4.663974	6.853480	2.971925	0.670172	.499043	2.969284

“Table II provides a summary of descriptive statistics of all the variables mentioned in Table no. I For all the variables mean, median, standard deviation, minimum ,maximum values and skewness and kurtosis are calculated. . Average return on total assets is 8.11 as compared to average return on equity of 15.89 and that of annual stock return is 29.7 percent. The median represents the middle value of the distribution and it is 7.44 for executive pay with a maximum of 9.21 and minimum of 3.69. The average size of the sample firms is 4.72

Table III Descriptive statistics of the Private Firms”

	LOG_EXEC	RETURN_...	RETURN_...	RETURN	TOBIN_Q	SIZE	BETA
Mean	7.530606	8.883682	17.48561	32.32799	4.802192	4.663142	0.961036
Median	7.532587	7.750000	16.92000	12.12471	3.449655	4.602201	0.920000
Maximum	9.218982	32.88000	427.7800	1924.403	50.75828	6.853480	2.640000
Minimum	4.602060	-15.73000	-1109.110	-97.37257	-47.99703	3.183327	0.140000
Std. Dev.	0.476983	7.239189	39.78618	131.5737	5.361253	0.622216	0.381910
Skewness	-0.389582	0.684747	-20.01032	7.656004	2.125066	0.638511	0.594075
Kurtosis	5.441329	3.529327	606.8810	88.10520	25.78917	3.282070	3.241894
Jarque-Bera	295.7969	97.09639	16497587	336792.4	24205.84	77.03689	66.22082
Probability	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
Sum	8140.585	9603.260	18901.94	34946.55	5191.170	5040.856	1038.880
Sum Sq. Dev.	245.7142	56598.33	1709575.	18696567	31042.47	418.1247	157.5236
Observations	1081	1081	1081	1081	1081	1081	1081

Table IV Descriptive statistics of the Public Firms

	LOG_EXEC	RETURN_...	RETURN_...	RETURN	TOBIN_Q	SIZE	BETA
Mean	6.591629	5.990000	12.32733	15.63509	1.971875	5.371440	1.073778
Median	6.675611	5.190000	12.34000	1.107011	1.484500	5.316547	1.020000
Maximum	7.660865	26.13000	38.83000	439.4100	18.14276	6.695523	1.950000
Minimum	3.698970	-5.660000	-29.78000	-87.53303	0.271666	3.756499	0.350000
Std. Dev.	0.494520	5.154166	9.636056	67.77684	1.909671	0.692220	0.365104
Skewness	-2.539298	0.770113	-0.626069	2.938307	5.067137	-0.191176	0.550326
Kurtosis	14.15725	4.638691	5.562696	15.85343	40.28719	2.350279	2.556095
Jarque-Bera	845.3041	28.44901	45.76084	1123.567	8398.339	3.196859	7.922738
Probability	0.000000	0.000001	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.202214	0.019037
Sum	889.8700	808.6500	1664.190	2110.737	266.2031	725.1444	144.9600
Sum Sq. Dev.	32.76972	3559.767	12442.38	615555.9	488.6772	64.20863	17.86237
Observations	135	135	135	135	135	135	135

Table III and IV present the descriptive statistics of Private and Public firms. A comparison of the two tables reveals several differences between the two groups.

“In terms of executive compensation, the average compensation for Public firms is 6.591629, while for Private firms, it is slightly higher at 7.530606. The maximum executive compensation observed in Public firms is 9.218982, whereas in Private firms, it reaches 7.660865. These figures indicate that, on average, Public firms have slightly lower executive compensation compared to Private firms, with a wider range of compensation observed in Private firms.

Furthermore, there are variations in the returns of Private and Public firms. The mean return for Private firms is 8.883862, significantly higher than the mean return for Public firms, which stands at 5.990000. The maximum return observed in Private firms is 32.88000, while in Public firms, it

reaches 26.13000. These statistics suggest that, on average, Private firms tend to have higher returns compared to Public firms, with greater variability in returns among Private firms.

These findings highlight the differences in executive compensation and returns between Private and Public firms, indicating potential variations in performance and financial outcomes between the two groups”

Correlation analysis

Karl Pearson's coefficient of correlation is used to examine the relationship between dependent and independent variables. In this study, the dependent variables include return on assets, return on net worth, and profit margins, while the independent variable is executive compensation. The coefficient of correlation, denoted by r , provides information about the direction and strength of the relationship between the variables.

If the value of r is positive, it indicates a direct relationship between the variables, meaning that as one variable increases, the other variable also tends to increase. Conversely, if the value of r is negative, it suggests an inverse relationship, where the variables move in opposite directions.

Based on the table, the results show a very insignificant positive relationship between executive compensation and both return on assets and return on net worth. This implies that there is a weak and non-significant tendency for higher executive compensation to be associated with higher values of return on assets and return on net worth. On the other hand, there is an insignificant negative relationship between executive compensation and profit margin, indicating that there is no meaningful association between executive compensation and profit margin in this study.

Table	V correlation matrix							
Correlation Probability	LOG_EXEC	RETURN	RETURN ...	RETURN ...	TOBIN_Q	LEVERAGE	BETA	SIZE
LOG_EXEC	1.000000 ----							
RETURN	0.027442 0.3331	1.000000 ----						
RETURN_ON_NE...	0.059442 0.0359	0.062523 0.0273	1.000000 ----					
RETURN_ON_TO...	0.096554 0.0006	0.133040 0.0000	0.386668 0.0000	1.000000 ----				
TOBIN_Q	0.118656 0.0000	0.114225 0.0001	0.138778 0.0000	0.461197 0.0000	1.000000 ----			
LEVERAGE	0.018738 0.5087	-0.036039 0.2036	-0.142492 0.0000	-0.507966 0.0000	-0.271647 0.0000	1.000000 ----		
BETA	-0.069382 0.0143	-0.006057 0.8309	-0.200619 0.0000	-0.461134 0.0000	-0.253235 0.0000	0.291306 0.0000	1.000000 ----	
SIZE	0.077166 0.0064	-0.049562 0.0803	-0.106894 0.0002	-0.295201 0.0000	-0.138769 0.0000	0.435028 0.0000	0.153819 0.0000	1.000000 ----

Table V presents correlation matrix of variables. It indicates executive pay is positively correlated with the variables like return on asset, return on net worth, return, Tobin q , leverage and size but it is negatively associated with risk factor

Table VI correlation matrix for Private firms

	LOG_EXEC	RETURN_...	RETURN_...	RETURN	TOBIN_Q	SIZE	BETA
LOG_E...	1	0.03828128...	0.04268070...	0.00107189...	0.05309704...	0.34988760...	-0.0210321...
RETU...	0.03828128...	1	0.37889781...	0.12606486...	0.49496130...	-0.2703116...	-0.4772982...
RETU...	0.04268070...	0.37889781...	1	0.05939211...	0.13884767...	-0.1059708...	-0.2029113...
RETURN	0.00107189...	0.12606486...	0.05939211...	1	0.13153258...	-0.0417428...	0.00048148...
TOBIN_Q	0.05309704...	0.49496130...	0.13884767...	0.13153258...	1	-0.1008524...	-0.2972820...
SIZE	0.34988760...	-0.2703116...	-0.1059708...	-0.0417428...	-0.1008524...	1	0.15995357...
BETA	-0.0210321...	-0.4772982...	-0.2029113...	0.00048148...	-0.2972820...	0.15995357...	1

Table VI presents correlation matrix of variables for Private firms. It indicates executive pay is positively correlated with the variables like return on asset, return on net worth, return, Tobin q, leverage and size but it is negatively associated with risk factor

Table VII correlation matrix for Public firms

	LOG_EXEC	RETURN_...	RETURN_...	RETURN	TOBIN_Q	SIZE	BETA
LOG_E...	1	-0.0428341...	0.07667793...	0.09259068...	0.25429675...	0.12360053...	0.02262424...
RETU...	-0.0428341...	1	0.80095176...	0.07714621...	0.40753046...	-0.3404573...	-0.2167015...
RETU...	0.07667793...	0.80095176...	1	0.09527610...	0.32995334...	-0.0832078...	-0.1841090...
RETURN	0.09259068...	0.07714621...	0.09527610...	1	0.09813503...	-0.0506675...	-0.0320977...
TOBIN_Q	0.25429675...	0.40753046...	0.32995334...	0.09813503...	1	-0.2929772...	0.16337717...
SIZE	0.12360053...	-0.3404573...	-0.0832078...	-0.0506675...	-0.2929772...	1	-0.0712851...
BETA	0.02262424...	-0.2167015...	-0.1841090...	-0.0320977...	0.16337717...	-0.0712851...	1

Table VII presents correlation matrix of variables for Public firms. It indicates executive pay is positively correlated with the variables like return on asset, return on net worth, return, Tobin q, leverage

The correlation matrix collated in table no. 6 and 7 exhibit executive compensation is more significantly correlated with size in case of Private firms than in case of Public firms

REGRESSION ANALYSIS

To investigate the relationship between executive compensation and firm performance the following equations have been used.

$$\text{PERF} = \alpha + \beta \text{LOG CEO}_{ti} + \beta_1 \text{RET}_{ti} + \beta_2 \text{ROA}_{ti} + \beta_3 \text{ROE}_{ti} + \beta_4 \text{LEV}_{ti} + \beta_5 \text{SIZE}_{ti} + \beta_6 \text{Q}_{ti} \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

For firm performance two measures will be used ROA and ROE. Therefore the specific equations are as follows which have been used in the previous studies such as Duffues and Kabir (2008)

$$\text{ROA} = \alpha + \beta \text{LOG CEO}_{ti} + \beta_1 \text{RET}_{ti} + \beta_2 \text{ROE}_{ti} + \beta_3 \text{LEV}_{ti} + \beta_4 \text{SIZE}_{ti} + \beta_5 \text{TOB}_{ti} + \beta_6 \text{Q}_{ti} \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

$$ROE = \alpha + \beta \text{ LOG CEO}_{ti} + \beta_1 \text{ RET}_{ti} + \beta_2 \text{ ROA}_{ti} + \beta_3 \text{ TOB}_{ti} + \beta_4 \text{ LEV}_{ti} + \beta_5 \text{ SIZE}_{ti} + \beta_6 \text{ Q}_{ti} \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

$$\text{RET} = \alpha + \beta \text{ LOG CEO}_{ti} + \beta_1 \text{ TOB}_{ti} + \beta_2 \text{ ROA}_{ti} + \beta_3 \text{ ROE}_{ti} + \beta_4 \text{ LEV}_{ti} + \beta_5 \text{ SIZE}_{ti} + \beta_6 \text{ Q}_{ti} \quad \text{Eq. (3)}$$

Hausman Test

A Hausman specification test is conducted to compare the suitability of a fixed effect model and a random effect model. The null hypothesis assumes that there is no correlation between individual effects and regressors, while the alternative hypothesis suggests that a fixed effect model is preferred if the null hypothesis is rejected.

In our case, if the probability (p-value) obtained from the Hausman test is more than 5%, we fail to reject the null hypothesis, indicating that the random effect model is appropriate. However, if the probability is less than 5%, we accept the alternative hypothesis, indicating that the fixed effect model is preferred.

Since the probability in our case is less than 5%, we accept the alternative hypothesis and conclude that the fixed effect model is more suitable for our analysis. We evaluate Equation (1) using FE estimators FOR Private firms only. The findings are detailed in Table no. VIII

Table no. VIII

Fixed effect model results using Return on total asset as dependent variable for PVT firms			
Variable	coefficient	Standard error	P value
Log _ Exec	12.69340	3.831934	.0010
Return on net worth	.027931	.0031323	.0000
Return	.000945	.000787	.2304
Tobin q	.293459	.032962	.0000
Leverage	-11.57125	1.854557	.0000
size	-2.372904	.829116	.0043
beta	-0.502710	.597018	.4000
Adjusted R ²	.810997		

Table VIII shows the result of Fixed effect model with Return on total asset as dependent variable for **Private firms**. Based on Table 8 results we can conclude that executive compensation, return_on_net_worth,, tobin_q, leverage and size have probability less than 5 % so they are significant variables which explain the dependent variable return on total asset. The value of R² is .810997 which indicates 81.09 percent of fluctuations in return on total asset can be explained by the executive compensation , return, return_on_net_worth, , tobin_q, leverage ,beta and size 18.89 percent of variation in executive compensation can be explained by other variables

We evaluate equation (2) using FE estimators FOR Private firms only. The findings are detailed in Table IX

Table no. IX

Fixed effect model results using Return on net worth as dependent variable for PVT firms			
Variable	coefficient	Standard error	P value
Log _ Exec	1.971475	3.721257	0.5964
Return on asset	2.919858	.326439	.0000
Return	.005666	.008055	.4820
Tobin q	-2.342947	.342748	.0000
Leverage	9.985515	19.364115	.6062
beta	-12.01796	6.093402	0.0489
size	4.339821	8.514422	.6104
Adjusted R ²	.345880		

Table IX9 presents the results of fixed effect model using return on net worth as dependent variable for Indian Firms The value of R² is .345880 the value of R² is less than 60 %so this model is not a good fit

We evaluate equation (3) using FE estimators FOR Private firms only. The findings are detailed in Table X

Fixed effect model results using Return as dependent variable for PVT firms			
Variable	coefficient	Standard error	P value
Log _ Exec	-10.25676	15.38552	.0449
Return on net worth	.096868	.137715	.4820
Return on assets	1.688970	1.407310	.2304
Tobin q	4.583034	1.445461	.0016
Leverage	115.9530	79.98684	.1475
size	-75.22212	35.12181	.0325
beta	85.22484	25.08962	.0007
Adjusted R ²	-.022604		

Table X presents the results of fixed effect model using return as dependent variable for Indian Firms The value of R² is -.022604 the value of R² is less than 60 % so this model is not a good fit

We evaluate equation (1) using FE estimators FOR Public firms only. The findings are detailed in Table XI

Table XI

Fixed effect model results using Return on total asset as dependent variable for Govt firms			
Variable	coefficient	Standard error	P value
Log _ Exec	22.95811	9.624468	.0189

Return on net worth	.315472	.019150	.0000
Return	.000418	.002004	.8352
Tobin q	.456044	.095476	.0000
Leverage	-10.56603	3.046700	.0008
size	-2.971367	1.928818	.1265
beta	-0.011195	0.675831	.9868
Adjusted R ²	.922321		

Table XI presents the results for public firms using return on total assets as the dependent variable. The findings indicate that executive compensation, return on net worth, Tobin's Q, and leverage are significant variables with a probability of less than 5%. This suggests that they play a significant role in explaining the variation in return on total assets. The R-squared value of 0.922321 indicates that 92.23% of the fluctuations in return on total assets can be explained by leverage, executive compensation, and return on net worth, while 7.77% of the variation is attributed to other variables.

We evaluate Equation (2) using fixed effects estimators for public firms only. The detailed findings can be found in Table XII.

Table no. XII

Fixed effect model results using Return on net worth as dependent variable for Govt firms			
Variable	coefficient	Standard error	P value
Log _ Exec	1.002917	1.289522	.4385
Return on total assets	2.303930	.139854	.0000
Return	-.002296	.005413	.6723
Tobin q	-.657069	.277905	.0200
Leverage	19.50355	8.488494	.0236
size	.403629	5.272633	.9391
beta	1.224153	1.8223662	.5033
Adjusted R ²	.837696		

Table XII presents the results for public firms using return on net worth as the dependent variable. The findings indicate that return on total assets, Tobin's Q, and leverage are significant variables with a probability of less than 5%. This suggests that they play a significant role in explaining the variation in return on net worth. However, the p-value for executive compensation is 0.4385, indicating that it is not a significant variable in determining return on net worth. The R-squared value of 0.837696 indicates that 83.76% of the fluctuations in return on net worth can be explained by leverage, executive compensation, and return on total assets, while 16.24% of the variation is attributed to other variables.

Table XIII presents the results of evaluating equation (3) using fixed effects estimators for public firms only. The detailed findings can be found in Table XII.

Fixed effect model results using Return as dependent variable for Govt firms			
Variable	coefficient	Standard error	P value
Log _ Exec	26.81934	23.48674	.2562
Return on total assets	1.019885	4.889111	.8352
Return on net worth	-.766957	1.807946	.6723
Tobin q	4.979358	5.192801	.3399
Leverage	-125.3581	158.6101	.4312
size	-97.40932	-1.015965	.3121
beta	31.07081	.934854	.3521
Adjusted R ²	-.095727		

Table XIII presents results using Return as dependent variable for **Public firms**. The value of R² is -.095727 which is less than 60 %so this model is not a good fit

CONCLUSION

This paper investigates the relationship between executive compensation and firm performance, with a specific focus on excessive executive compensation. The objective is to examine whether CEO compensation is associated with firm performance. Various metrics, including return on assets, return on net worth, return, and Tobin's Q, are utilized to assess the correlation between CEO total compensation and firm variables. The sample consists of 199 firms listed on the NIFTY, categorized as Indian and foreign firms. The results reveal a positive correlation between executive compensation and firm performance, particularly when measured by the accounting metric of return on total assets. However, when market-based measures are used to evaluate the pay-performance relationship among the sample firms, no statistically significant association is found. Jaiswall and Bhattacharyya (2016) find that ownership structure plays a significant role in the pay-performance relationship among Indian firms. Previous studies by Jaiswall and Firth (2009) and Raithatha and Komera (2016) explore ownership structure in the context of family-owned and business-affiliated groups. In this study, the sample is further divided into private and public firms listed on the NIFTY, revealing variations in executive compensation and returns between the two groups. Private firms exhibit higher average compensation. Statistically significant relationships are observed between return on assets and executive compensation for both private and public firms. Additionally, firm size and leverage are identified as significant variables influencing firm performance. The correlation matrix indicates a stronger correlation between executive compensation and firm size for private firms compared to public firms.

Limitations and Future Research:

It is important to note that the analysis and findings are based on data collected from 2011 to 2017 and involve a sample of 199 firms from the NIFTY 500, excluding financial service firms due to

regulatory considerations. The study has limitations such as a relatively small sample size and the lack of consistent data throughout the study period. Nonetheless, this research contributes to the understanding of the relationship between executive compensation and firm performance, shedding light on the various variables that impact empirical research. It serves as a foundation for future studies in this area.

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